

Psychometrics for a Cybernetic Theory of Human Agency

Abstract

Despite its centrality to psychology, human agency lacks an accepted definition or reliable measurement. This paper proposes an operational definition grounded in cybernetics and control theory, drawing on Michael Levin's framework of cognitive lightcones and Karl Friston's active inference. Agency is decomposed into three factors: agentic scope (the temporal, spatial, and complexity scale of goals pursued), agentic capacity (the ability to act toward those goals), and agentic environment (environmental constraints on goal achievement). The paper focuses on developing the psychometric basis of agentic scope, linking it to established constructs including Big Five personality (interpreted through DeYoung's Cybernetic Big Five Theory), general intelligence, the Agency and Communion value dimensions, identity formation, persuadability, and risk preference. A review of the literature finds that agentic scope is predicted by Assertiveness, Industriousness, and Intellect, moderated by Openness and risk tolerance, and constrained by Neuroticism (particularly Withdrawal) and conformity. Intelligence is central through its effects on perception, world-modeling, and the capacity for rational evaluation of competing claims. The paper also identifies variables outside the Big Five and IQ that bear on agency, including the autism-schizotypy spectrum as characterized by computational psychiatry, and proposes that identity formation processes distinguish between agents who select goals from an existing incentive landscape and those who construct novel goal hierarchies. Directions for future research include purpose-built scales for the spatial, temporal, and complexity dimensions of agentic scope, empirical investigation of the proposed striver-Nietzschean distinction, and extension of the framework to agentic capacity and environment.

Apart from intelligence, agency is perhaps the most important psychological trait. Intelligence is the ability to construct accurate mental models from limited information; agency is the ability to exert your will and accomplish things in the world (or to have a will to exert in the first place). The Great Man theory of history, or the more recent Great Founder theory,^[1] both reduce to the claim that the most agentic individuals determine the direction society takes, and the distribution of agency across a population shapes its economic and institutional outcomes. Despite this, while IQ is the most reliable measurement in all of differential psychology, there is no comparable measure of agency; no accepted definition exists in the psychometric literature. One review remarks that "probably no concept is as central to psychology and its aspirations, yet as poorly articulated, as that on human agency."^[2] This paper proposes an operational definition of human agency grounded in cybernetics, and links it to both established psychometric constructs like Big Five personality and IQ, as well as emerging research in active inference and computational psychiatry, with the aim of providing a framework that can bridge the gap from the study of agentic systems to differential psychology.

1 The State of the Literature

The existing literature on agency is in poor condition and rife with jingle fallacies. A 2021 review of psychometric instruments for assessing agency found 26 different instruments used from 2000 to 2020.^[3] These instruments were not at all cohesive, with some being merely five items or even a single item, or otherwise only dubiously related to human agency broadly conceived. There was no evidence of any effort to build up a nomological network to define human agency.¹ Instead many of the papers were narrowly focused on measures that could be used to justify public health or social justice interventions. In these cases the instruments used were really measuring life satisfaction, or women's perceived freedom, or commitment to take action against racism. None of the measures incorporated IQ or personality, despite these being of central importance to any measure of agency that would claim face validity. Elsewhere the literature conflates agency with free will and digresses into philosophical discussions, or else describes agency as the "dynamic interplay" of routine, purpose, and judgement without grounding these terms in operational empiricism.^[4] There-

¹The concept of a nomological network was introduced by Cronbach and Meehl (1955), in order to define latent psychological variables which cannot be directly measured, but can be described by the lawful relationships between their observable characteristics: 1. Scientifically speaking, to "make clear what something is" means to set forth the laws in which it occurs. We shall refer to the interlocking system of laws which constitute a theory as a nomological network. 2. The laws in a nomological network may relate (a) observable properties or quantities to each other; or (b) theoretical constructs to observables; or (c) different theoretical constructs to one another. These "laws" may be statistical or deterministic.^[53]

fore, while this paper will draw at length from the psychological literature, it finds little value in the existing literature on agency as such.

2 Cybernetic Agents

Although we are interested in an empirical definition of human agency, it is helpful to begin by providing a more abstract definition of agency, of which human agency is a special case. Michael Levin defines a Self as a coherent system that acts to accomplish goals in a problem space, where Selfhood is independent of the specific material substrate and problem space.^[5] Agency is then defined in terms of cybernetics and control theory as the use of homeostatic perception-action loops to maintain (or equivalently minimize deviation from) set points, with the actions and set points defining the problem space. Under this framework stress is cast as the result of deviation from a set point. "Overall, increases of agency are driven by mechanisms that scale up stress—the scope of states that an agent can possibly be stressed about (in the sense of pressure to take corrective action)." Every agent, whether it is a single cell, an animal, or a human, has a cognitive lightcone that defines the spatial and temporal scale that agent is capable of affecting: "the scale of events about which they care and the boundary of states that they can possibly represent or work to change." The measure of agency for an arbitrary cybernetic system is then a function of the problem space it is working in, as well as the spatial, temporal, and complexity scale of the aims it is capable of affecting in that space.

Just as cells solve problems in transcriptional space or tissues solve problems in morphological spaces, humans and other macroscopic animals solve problems in behavioural space. For a human, then, *demonstrated agency* is a product of three factors: *agentic scope*, *agentic capacity*, and *agentic environment*. In brief, agentic scope is defined by the temporal extent, spatial extent, and complexity of the goals an individual attempts to pursue. Agentic capacity is the capacity for the individual to take action towards these goals, and may be defined in anatomical, physiological, and psychological terms. Agentic environment is the environment in which the individual is pursuing his goals, which may be more or less conducive to their achievement. Demonstrated agency is the actual level of agency an individual achieves in the real world, which may be constrained by limitations in one or more of the three basal factors. In this sense, demonstrated agency is defined similarly to Eysenck's conception of genius, which is the product of high levels of intelligence, creativity, and work capacity; an individual possessing high levels of agentic scope and agentic capacity, coupled with a favourable agentic environment, may achieve high levels of demonstrated agency. Similarly to genius, while it may be possible to recognize high levels of demonstrated agency, it is

not necessarily amenable to direct quantification and cardinal (or even ordinal) comparison. It is however possible to identify constructs in the literature that make it possible to quantify agentic scope. This paper will begin the task of developing the psychometric basis of agentic scope, with future work elaborating agentic capacity and environment.

3 What Kind of Cybernetic Agents Are Humans?

Karl Friston's Free Energy Principle from neuroscience integrates cleanly with the cybernetic view of human agency. The Free Energy Principle states that the brain operates to reduce prediction error in perceptions. This can either happen through perceptual inference, updating the brain's world model to accord with perceptions, or active inference, taking action to alter what is perceived in order to make it match predictions better (either by changing the things you choose to perceive, or changing the world itself to make it match your predictions). In this sense, the homeostatic set-point is zero entropy: perfect prediction about what will be perceived. Given the link between action and perception, active inference frames behaviour as a pure inference problem, where you take the actions that are most likely to lead to your predictions being satisfied.^[6]

As a mathematical formalism, active inference is related to reinforcement learning. In reinforcement learning, an agent has a policy (a set of actions it can take) and certain reward states that it tries to access. In active inference, rather than a state possessing a reward value, reward is simply encoded as a higher predicted likelihood of occupying that state. Thus there is a one-to-one correspondence between the states the agent predicts it will occupy most, and the states the agent finds most rewarding.² All action is then undertaken to actualize those predictions, conditional on the set of behaviours the agent is capable of enacting, and the world model possessed by the agent.

As a foundational model of the human cybernetic system,³ active inference operates at a level below that of psychometrics, however this level is still capable of producing insights into the nature of human agency. For instance, depersonalization disorder is characterized by the feeling of being an outside observer of one's own thoughts and actions, i.e. the loss of the feeling of agency. This is explained in light of active infer-

²Note that as a mathematical abstraction active inference is not making claims about the phenomenology of reward nor is it arguing that reward is encoded in a unitary way physiologically. Different hormonal or neurotransmitter reward systems may combine to produce the same effect mathematically.

³The theory as presented does not require active inference to be fully correct in the final analysis, however it is a useful model to frame human behaviour, and other cybernetic neuroscientific models could also be slotted into this spot with some retooling to the connections between other aspects of the theory.

ence as an inability to attenuate the experience of perceptions resulting from our own actions.^[7] When we act, we expect to perceive certain things as a result (e.g. the sensation of gripping a coffee cup), and normally our brains pay little attention to these expected perceptions. When the salience of these predicted sensory inputs is not correctly attenuated, it presents phenomenologically as if another agent were responsible for your behaviour.

While the phenomenology of volitional action is a relevant aspect of agency's nomological network, it does not directly contribute to being able to quantify human agency more broadly. More immediately relevant is how the free energy principle models learning as a Bayesian optimization process. The way in which agents learn representations of their environment and of other agents is a core aspect of their cybernetic functioning, and one that is not measurable through psychometric means. Psychometrics use surveys or tests to produce standardized scores of latent (not directly measurable) variables, like personality or intelligence. On the other hand, Bayesian learning is assessed with cognitive neuroscience tasks that statistically model the way people update their beliefs in response to incoming information. In one such task, users are instructed to play a game guessing where payloads will be dropped by a helicopter flying above the clouds. The location of the helicopter itself is unknown, and the payload locations are normally distributed around the helicopter's location. Throughout the game, the helicopter moves (the mean of the distribution changes) and the spread of the payloads changes (the variance of the distribution changes). From the game data, researchers fit a hierarchical Gaussian filter model to understand how different people update their beliefs over time, with parameters for how uncertain the environment is, how quickly it changes over time, etc. From this data we can characterize different learning parameters between clinical populations, for instance people with autism overestimate the volatility of the sensory environment,^[8] and people with schizotypy are less responsive to statistical regularities in the sensory environment.^[9]

This research is currently in its early stages, with hierarchical Gaussian filter models only being applied in experimental research in the past 10 years. However, they will eventually enable us to quantify the parameters that underlie psychological phenomena that were previously treated theoretically under the framework of active inference. The most important one being the variation in responses to prediction error that underlies the autism-schizotypy axis.

The autism-schizotypy axis is one example of a psychological variable pertaining to agency that is outside the scope of both Big 5 and IQ. This axis is understood under the framework of active inference as normal variation in how much weight the brain assigns to prediction errors arising from incoming perceptual information. While at either extreme this axis manifests as psychopathology (autism and schizophrenia),

within the normal range it simply represents a dimension of individual differences. Broadly speaking, autism is characterized by a low threshold for prediction error, and schizophrenia by a high threshold. In autism this manifests as a tendency to experience sensory overload, difficulty responding to changing circumstances, social deficits (social situations are difficult to predict), and an affinity for rules-based systems and routines that are very predictable. In schizotypy this manifests as the feeling that mundane phenomena possess personal significance, unusual sensory experiences, and magical thinking.

This is an emerging paradigm for characterizing the autism-schizotypy spectrum. At this time most research has been on clinical populations, with relatively little research looking at how the spectrum manifests outside the pathological extremes. While there are psychometrics that assess autism and schizotypy, for instance asking about autistic fixations or strange sensory experiences, the literature connecting them with agency or life outcomes outside of clinical populations is minimal. We will need to look elsewhere for suitable psychometrics for this task.

4 Cybernetics and Personality

Psychometrics is the study of latent psychological traits, like intelligence or personality. Two of the most commonly applied psychometric instruments are IQ tests and personality tests, with the most common model of personality being the Big Five. Both of these measures can be directly incorporated into a cybernetic model. Cybernetic Big 5 Theory^[10] offers a unifying view, identifying psychological traits as evolutionarily selected cybernetic parameters. Traits reflect the density distribution of states that the agent frequently occupies. For instance, Extraversion is associated with the frequency of gregariousness and Neuroticism with depressed mood. This fits nicely with active inference, with traits as biologically encoded variables defining the prior expectation of states the agent will occupy. Below the level of traits, characteristic adaptations are specific learned patterns of behaviour that are stably expressed in response to stimuli, for instance the tasks performed at one's job or the way one interacts with their spouse. Characteristic adaptations are influenced by traits, though not determined by them; mismatch between the characteristic adaptations demanded by the environment and psychological traits can cause stress (prediction error) over time, e.g. an introvert in a sales job, or a callous person in a caretaking role.

At the top level of the Big Five hierarchy are the Big Two metatraits of Plasticity and Stability. Plasticity comprises the shared variance of Extraversion and Openness, while Stability comprises the shared variance of Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, and (inverse) Neuroticism (also called Emotional Stability). Broadly speaking, Plastic-

ity is the cybernetic parameter controlling activation of exploratory behaviours, while Stability controls suppression of disruptive behaviours. One study assessed how Plasticity and Stability affected the frequency of 386 behaviours, over and above the effects of any of the individual Big Five traits. Plasticity was significantly correlated with 126 behaviours, of which 98

4.1 Extraversion

As a component of Plasticity, Extraversion reflects sensitivity to reward. Contrary to popular belief, the trait is not fundamentally about socializing. However, since humans are highly social animals many rewards must be pursued or achieved in social contexts, meaning the nature of an individual's goal-directed behaviour influences their social behaviour. Extraversion is comprised of Assertiveness, which reflects incentive reward and goal pursuit, and Enthusiasm, which reflects consumptive reward. The difference between the two is characterized by wanting versus liking – having strong desires you want to fulfill versus taking pleasure in experiences like eating, drinking, sex, or socializing. Both aspects are underpinned by dopamine, however Enthusiasm is likely also underpinned by the endogenous opioid reward system. In the context of active inference, Assertiveness places a strong prior on goal-achieved states, making goal-directed behaviour the policy that most reduces prediction error. Enthusiasm places a corresponding prior on consummatory states, driving reward-seeking behaviour.

4.2 Openness

The other component of Plasticity is Openness, which reflects engagement with information and perceptual stimuli, motivated by the dopaminergic reward value of information. Its first aspect is Openness to Experience, which is associated with aesthetic appreciation, and as a cybernetic parameter may reflect attention to perceptual patterns in time and space. The second aspect is Intellect, which is associated with engagement with abstract logical or semantic information. Intellect is the only aspect of the Big Five that is correlated with IQ, at about $r = 0.3$ to 0.4 .^[15] The relationship between cognitive ability and personality highlights that personality is not disjoint from ability; if personality is a density distribution of states, then agents with greater abilities are more likely to find themselves in the corresponding states. Under active inference, Openness reflects a high weighting of epistemic value – the expected information gain from a course of action. When reducing uncertainty about the world model is itself rewarding, contemplation and exploration become the policies that most reduce the agent's expected free energy.

4.3 Agreeableness

The first component of Stability is Agreeableness, which unlike Extraversion is a fundamentally social dimension, reflecting the drive to seek affiliation and harmony with others. Its first aspect is Compassion, which represents the drive to seek affiliative intimacy with others, underpinned by the oxytocin and opioid systems. Its second aspect is Politeness, which reflects the suppression of aggression and violation of social norms. Compassion and Enthusiasm are correlated almost as strongly with each other as they are with Politeness or Assertiveness, respectively, likely due to the shared influence of the opioid system.^[16] In the context of active inference, Agreeableness encodes strong priors on affiliative social states, making policies that maintain interpersonal harmony the ones that most reduce prediction error, even when this requires sacrificing other goals.

4.4 Conscientiousness

The second component of Stability is Conscientiousness, which reflects the ability and tendency to prioritize long-term goals over more immediate desires. Its first aspect is Industriousness, which represents the prioritization of non-immediate goals. Its second aspect is Orderliness, which represents the avoidance of entropy by following rules set by self or others. From the perspective of active inference, Conscientiousness operates as a higher-order prior that maintains commitment to the currently selected long-term policy, reducing interference from competing short-term impulses. Extraversion and Conscientiousness together predict physical activity levels;^[17] people who perceive more rewards (Extraversion) and prioritize longer-term goals (Conscientiousness) display higher levels of activity in general.

4.5 Neuroticism

The last component of Stability is (inverse) Neuroticism, also called Emotional Stability. Neuroticism reflects defensive responses to uncertainty, threat, and punishment. Its first aspect is Volatility, which reflects active defence to avoid or eliminate threats. Its second aspect is Withdrawal, which reflects passive avoidance: the inhibition of goal-directed behaviour in response to uncertainty or error. From the perspective of active inference, individuals high in Neuroticism upweight the salience and perceived severity of threatening stimuli, whether these are threats (a potential loss) or punishments (a realized loss), leading to both active defensive behaviours and passive disengagement from goal pursuit. Withdrawal in particular is directly antagonistic to agency.

4.6 Incremental Validity and the Bandwidth-Fidelity Tradeoff

In order to be quantifiable, agency must be expressible in terms of Big 5, IQ, or other measurable variables. Indeed, there is good reason to believe that it is, and that Big 5 and IQ together will be sufficient to explain a large proportion of the variation in agency observed between humans. This naturally raises the question of what benefit there would be to discover additional specialized psychometrics related to agency, if Big 5 and IQ already explain most of the variance. The first reason is that more specific measures, perhaps nested inside the Big 5, may provide incremental validity improvements beyond what the Big 5 offers. This is a consequence of the bandwidth-fidelity tradeoff; since Big 5 scales are optimized to measure the general case (i.e. broad bandwidth), they will consequently be worse at approximating actual behaviours of interest that may more directly pertain to agency.^[18] For example, if Extraversion is an important determinant of agency, but primarily due to the contribution of Assertiveness, then assessing Assertiveness specifically will be a better measure than assessing all aspects of Extraversion.⁴ We want to discover the minimal covering set of measures that relate to agency, rather than a set of measures that cover agency but also contain unnecessary elements. In this way the nomological network discovered will be as parsimonious as possible.

5 Agentic Scope

5.1 Perception

Under the cybernetic model, agentic scope pertains to the setpoints that the agent attempts to maintain. In order to maintain a setpoint, the agent must first be capable of perceiving it. Without perception it is impossible to detect deviation from it, nor to assess the effectiveness of any corrective action. It is self-evident that people who lack normal perceptual abilities, for instance the blind or the deaf, have a reduced scope of agency. These disabilities have estimated Disability Weights of 0.19 and 0.21 respectively^[19] – corresponding to a roughly 20

The range of perceptual disabilities that constrain agentic scope goes beyond the most obvious disabilities. In a social environment, inability to read social cues impairs the ability to defend interpersonal setpoints, like reputational maintenance or mate retention. The impact of any perceptual disability is always relative to the agentic environment in which an agent acts. In a solitary environment, an individual with face

⁴Or perhaps Enthusiasm produces in goal-driven behaviour in a short-term, self-limited way to increase consumption, while assertiveness increases goal-driven behaviour in general including for long-term non-consumptive goals.

blindness and an inability to perceive social cues would not suffer any disadvantage relative to an individual not suffering from these disabilities. Therefore, an individual may attempt to locate or construct an agentic environment that is conducive to the particular perceptual faculties that they possess. However, human lifestyles and environments are all broadly similar in terms of the perceptual abilities required to navigate them, and so a deficiency in a standard perceptual ability can be considered as reducing agentic scope.

In general, the quality of perception constrains the quality of agentic action. Charles Spearman, who discovered the general intelligence factor g , also theorized that there was a general factor of sensory discrimination s which had a near-perfect correspondence with g . Modern research investigating this question reveals that an s factor can be extracted from different sensory perception tasks, which correlates with g at $r = 0.68$.^[20] More intelligent individuals will display more fine-grained perceptual abilities, which enable detecting smaller deviations from setpoints, as well as constructing more detailed world models and making more detailed predictions within those models. General intelligence is therefore central to agentic scope, with general sensory discrimination offering a potential incremental improvement above the agency conferred by intelligence.

5.2 Agency and Communion

Assuming equal perceptual abilities, individuals will still vary in the values they hold, and hence the kinds of setpoints they will choose to defend. Agency and Communion are two such measures that exist in the psychometric literature. Agency is defined roughly as 'getting ahead' and Communion as 'getting along'. The terms were first proposed by Bakan in 1966,^[21] and since then have attracted significant research interest. Despite the early introduction of the concepts, the first scale to directly measure them was only developed in 2012.^[22] That work was, nonetheless, also able to identify agency and communion as superordinate factors in four independent datasets. The first, Richards' (1966) life goals data, identified the two factors: "The highest loading agentic life goals involved leadership, power, expertise, success, and economic interests. The highest loading communal life goals involved fulfilling relational and religious obligations and commitments, seeking 'purpose' in life, and sacrificing for others." The second, based on Roberts and Robins (2000) Life Goals Data, identified economic, hedonistic, and political life goals with an agency factor, and social, religious, and aesthetic life goals as a communion factor. The third and fourth data sets, using the Portrait of Values questionnaire in the European Social Survey and a sample of Canadian college students, likewise identified two identical superordinate factors which explained 49-52.6

The paper subsequently develops a 24-item scale for Agency and Communion, based on a 9-point Likert scale from *not important to me* to *highly important to me*. The three items loading most highly on the Agency scale are *status*, *power*, and *superiority*, while the three items loading most highly on the Communion scale are *compassion*, *civility*, and *altruism*. Notably, the largest gender differences were found on the *superiority* ($d = 0.63$ in favour of men) and *compassion* ($d = 0.44$ in favour of women) items. The whole-scale gender differences are not reported, however all but one item on the agency scale exhibits a male bias, and similarly all but one item on the communion scale exhibits a female bias. Additionally, Agency and Communion correlate with the respective gender on the Bem Sex Role Inventory scale at $r=0.43$ and $r=0.48$. While dark triad traits correlate with the Agency scale, the correlation is stronger with Agency minus Communion (between $r=0.43$ and $r=0.55$), which the authors interpret as evidence for the dark triad traits being agency unconstrained by pro-social values.^[22]

A separate study undertook to construct an Agency and Communion scale out of items from the Big Five Inventory scale.^[23] Using four different scale construction methods, it was able to display convergent validity with existing Agency scales, and correlations that were roughly equal to the correlations between the existing scales. The Agency scales used Extraversion (Assertiveness) questions, as well as Openness questions and in two of the scales, a Neuroticism question related to stress tolerance. The Communion scale on the other hand employed almost entirely Agreeableness questions, and the odd Conscientiousness question about being a hard worker. This study also found, in line with previous research, that Agency and Communion correlated with each other, at between $r=0.3$ and $r=0.4$. However, the correlations were substantially attenuated when controlling for self-esteem, suggesting that the correlation is a result of general positive self-evaluation leading to inflated self-report measures. Combined with the previous study, it demonstrates a significant overlap between Agency scales whether operationalized as life goals, values, or personality traits.

Agency and Communion have previously been compared to Plasticity and Stability as possible higher-order factors of the Big Five. However, the study that constructed agency and communion scales out of Big 5 questions found that Agency was correlated with both Plasticity and Stability ($r = 0.71$ and $r = 0.74$, respectively) while Communion was most correlated with a composite of Agreeableness and Conscientiousness rather than with Stability as a whole ($r = 0.78$ compared to $r = 0.58$). This suggests that Agency and Communion are particular interstitial measures, as opposed to mapping cleanly onto metatraits. Agency and Communion are however captured as Big Two factors when looking at measures related to social perception; Agency and Communion may capture two crucial dimensions when assessing others: how com-

petent are they to act, and how positively or negatively are they disposed to you? For instance, Agency and Communion were identified as common factors using a lexical analysis across nine languages.^[24] Investigations of social judgement also find two fundamental dimensions aligning with Agency and Communion (also called competence and warmth in this context).^[25] Types of socially-desirable responding similarly find two types of self-enhancement, either along agentic or communal lines, which are measured via Impression Management scales.^[26]

While Agency is a fundamental dimension of social judgement, research indicates that Agency (related to agentic scope) is both distinct from and more important to status perception than competence (agentic capacity).^[27] This may be because anyone at any level of the social hierarchy may display competence in their work, but only those at the top are expected to be highly agentic. The relationship is bi-directional: those with higher hierarchical position are judged to be more agentic (but not necessarily more competent), and those with more agentic qualities are inferred to possess higher social standing.

It is also likely that agentic scope, as proxied by an Agency measure, is related to real life outcomes, for instance career success, independent of actual competence (agentic capacity). One conceptual study used surveys to identify adjectives that were indicative of competence (e.g. *meticulous, skillful*) or agency (e.g. *ambitious, enterprising*).^[28] Four profiles were then built of accountants who were described as either high or low in both competence and agency, and study participants were asked how likely each accountant was to be promoted. It was found that the profiles high in agency and low in competence were considered more likely to be promoted than those high in competence but low in agency. While this was a conceptual study employing artificial profiles and no real-world measures, it nonetheless lends credence to the theory that agentic scope and agentic capacity are separate things, and may each be independently predictive of life outcomes.

While these are lab studies on social judgement rather than studies employing real-world measures and endpoints, they nonetheless demonstrate that agentic scope and agentic capacity are distinct, and to the extent that social status is determined by the judgements of others (e.g. in hiring, promotion, or showing deference) these findings are in fact relevant to actual outcomes. The strongest longitudinal evidence linking agency measures to real-world endpoints comes from a cohort of 1,930 German university graduates tracked from graduation across five waves over ten years.⁵ Agency and Communion were assessed at career entry with the Personal Attributes Question-

⁵This is the BELA-E (Berufliche Laufbahntwicklung von Akademikerinnen und Akademikern) cohort from the University of Erlangen, the subject of multiple publications. See Abele (2003), Abele & Spurk (2009, 2011).

naire, a trait scale in which respondents rate themselves on adjectives like *decisive*, *independent*, *self-confident*, and *stands up well under pressure*. Agency at age 27 predicted objective career success – operationalized as a composite of income and hierarchical status – over the following decade ($\beta=0.10$).^[29] Communion had no impact on career success. Both Agency and Communion demonstrated test-retest reliability at levels expected for stable psychological traits, at $r = 0.70$ and $r = 0.68$ respectively over 18 months.^[30] A separate analysis of the same cohort assessed career-advancement goals like wanting status, influence, or financial success and found that these predicted both salary and hierarchical position over seven years ($\beta=0.08$ to 0.11), but also predicted lower career satisfaction ($\beta=-0.10$) despite higher objective attainment.^[31] This accords with the cognitive lightcone framing of agentic scope as the scope of states the agent can be stressed about; the lack of satisfaction is the driver for further advancement. Communion predicted parenthood for both sexes ($\beta\approx 0.17$), while agency predicted only fatherhood ($\beta=0.12$). This fits the evolutionary logic of male intrasexual competition, and is consistent with the positive correlation between Agency measures and male sex roles referenced above. Taken together these lines of evidence indicate that Agency and Communion are useful indicators of the setpoints that humans defend, with implications across the lifespan.

5.3 Identity

Given the capacity to perceive deviation from setpoints in a given domain, the next question is the origin of those setpoints – whether they are endogenous or exogenous. If a student is working to become a doctor, is this an expression of his intrinsic desire, a mercenary drive towards an arbitrary but high-status profession, or conformity to his family's expectations?

At the most basic level, all individuals act to satisfy innate drives like hunger or safety without which they would perish. Above this baseline, higher-order goals vary in their origin and can be arranged along a spectrum from entirely exogenous to entirely endogenous. The conformist has his setpoints determined directly by others; his goals are whatever is expected of someone in his social position. The striver selects among the setpoints that the environment makes available and pursues them agentially, taking the incentive landscape as given and optimizing within it. The Nietzschean discovers or creates his own setpoints and niche-constructs his environment to support them. This last mode is an instance of second-order cybernetics: rather than monitoring distance from existing setpoints, the agent modifies which setpoints are worth monitoring in the first place.

Constant et al. (2019) explains conformity within active inference through the con-

cept of *deontic value*.^[32] Career paths, institutional roles, status hierarchies, and social norms function as cached computations: the expensive work of determining what to value has already been performed by the community and encoded in its institutions. Conformity is the state of affairs in which these cached values dominate an agent's policy selection. The striver treats the deontic landscape as informational rather than prescriptive, evaluating socially cached goals against his own reward sensitivities and selecting among them. The Nietzschean operates on the feedback loop itself – by constructing new niches, he creates deontic cues that reshape the available goals for others.

Existing psychometric scales do not capture the proposed distinction between the striver and the Nietzschean. Scales from self-determination theory measure whether motivation *feels* internal or external rather than whether the goals themselves are novel creations or selections from a pre-existing menu. A striver who has thoroughly internalized the incentive structure of his environment will score identically to someone who arrived at novel goals through independent reflection. The distinction is genealogical (who determined this was worth wanting?) rather than phenomenological (does wanting it feel like my choice?). Despite this limitation, we can still assess the relationship between psychometric measures, conformity, and identity.

DeYoung et al. (2002) operationalized conformity based on Paulhus' Impression Management scale and Eysenck's Lie scale.^[13] Both scales ask respondents to report negative behaviours like cheating, lying, or littering. While the Impression Management scale was designed to measure response bias from social desirability, it also measures genuine variance in these traits. Additionally, there is evidence that people high in desirable responding are likewise attentive to social expectations. The study found that conformity was substantially predicted by Stability (and all subtraits) and negatively predicted (with borderline significance) by Plasticity. This accords with the cybernetic interpretation: Stability inhibits behaviours including those that deviate from social norms, while Plasticity promotes exploration which may lead to norm violation.

There is also evidence that Agency and Communion are related to conformity in the context of religion. A study of 187,957 individuals across 11 European countries found that within religious cultures, Communion was predictive of higher religiosity while Agency was predictive of irreligiosity. The trend was opposite in irreligious countries, where Communion predicted atheism and Agency predicted religiosity. Communal people adopt the societal values that they are immersed in, whereas agentic people are more likely to adopt heterodox values, regardless of whether the mainstream culture is religious or irreligious.^[33]

Beyond conformity, there is the broader question of how identity itself should be un-

derstood cybernetically. Identity can be defined as the existing suite of characteristic adaptations an individual displays, as well as a probability distribution over the kinds of characteristic adaptations he may display in the future in different scenarios. The likelihood of future characteristic adaptations corresponds to values – one possible characteristic adaptation is to become a thief, which an individual may consider unlikely if it is contrary to their values. Thus identity is the things an agent currently does, as well as a set of things the agent would or would not do in the future, as circumstances change. Identity and its associated predictions can be encoded as autobiographical narrative, which is a multi-agent, multi-timescale predictive instrument, compatible with active inference.^[34] The suite of current and potential future adaptations can be formed in conformity with the deontic structure of the social environment, or self-determined.

The psychometric study of identity originates with Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, which posits that adolescents must resolve an identity crisis by committing to a coherent set of values, goals, and roles. James Marcia operationalized this in 1966 by defining two dimensions, commitment and exploration, and crossing them to produce four identity statuses: Achievement (explored, then committed), Moratorium (exploring, not yet committed), Foreclosure (committed without exploring), and Diffusion (neither exploring nor committed). The most commonly used instrument based on this model is the Extended Objective Measure of Ego Identity Status (EOMEIS), which investigates identity in the domains of politics, career, religion, and intimate relationships with items like *"I've never really questioned my religion. If it's right for my parents it must be right for me"* and *"It took me a long time to decide but now I know for sure what direction to move in for a career."*

There are problems with the psychometric rigour of Marcia's approach. The four statuses are derived by dichotomizing continuous scales into theoretical quadrants rather than empirically validating the resulting categories. Moratorium and diffusion are so highly correlated that they may not be distinct,^[35] and the identity literature has largely been developed by sociologists with limited psychometric expertise. Luyckx et al. (2005) addressed the first problem by unpacking commitment and exploration into four continuous dimensions: commitment making (choosing), identification with commitment (internalization), exploration in breadth (scanning alternatives), and exploration in depth (evaluating existing commitments).^[36] A subsequent paper added a fifth dimension, ruminative exploration (unproductive cycling without resolution), and formalized the five-dimension instrument as the Dimensions of Identity Development Scale (DIDS).^[37] The DIDS asks respondents domain-general questions like *"I know what I want to do with my future"* (commitment making) or *"I work out for myself if the goals I put forward in life really suit me"* (exploration in depth). Statuses were then

derived empirically via cluster analysis rather than theoretical fiat. The clusters recovered Achievement, Moratorium, and Foreclosure, but split Marcia's diffusion into two types: a pathological form (Diffuse Diffusion – uncommitted, distressed) and a well-adjusted but incurious form (Carefree Diffusion – moderate behavioural commitment, no exploration, low Openness and Conscientiousness).

Klimstra et al. (2013) mapped all five DIDS dimensions onto the thirty facets of the NEO-PI-R Big Five scale, and the results are consistent with the previously discussed relationship between Agency and the Big Five.^[38] All facets of Conscientiousness were significantly associated with the commitment and exploration dimensions. Achievement Striving specifically was the single most important personality variable: positively associated with both commitment dimensions (.43-.46; all values are β s), both productive exploration dimensions (.36), and negatively with ruminative exploration (-.21). Among Extraversion facets, Assertiveness was the strongest predictor of commitment making (.22) and identification with commitment (.24), and the strongest negative predictor of rumination (-.25). Warmth and Positive Emotions – which load on Enthusiasm but share common variance with Agreeableness and grounding in the opioid reward system – also predicted commitment (.16-.26) and productive exploration (.20-.28). By contrast, Excitement Seeking had no significant association with any identity dimension, and Gregariousness predicted only less rumination (-.18). This suggests that the facets of Extraversion that scaffold identity formation are those associated with goal pursuit and general positive emotionality rather than consumptive reward per se. Openness predicted all forms of exploration, including the maladaptive ruminative form, but did not predict commitment. Another study using Marcia's original four statuses found that Foreclosure's strongest correlate was low Openness ($r = -.50$).^[35] Together these support the cybernetic framing of Openness as information bandwidth which does not by itself product goal-directed action, but that in the absence of Openness individuals must default to conforming to default identities provided by their environments.

With the exception of Openness the personality substrate of productive exploration was largely non-overlapping with ruminative exploration. Withdrawal-adjacent Neuroticism facets (Vulnerability .32, Anxiety .31, Depression .23) and Politeness-adjacent Agreeableness facets (Compliance .15, Modesty .13) predicted rumination, while Compassion-adjacent facets (Altruism .20-.26, Tender-mindedness .14-.26) predicted productive exploration. Productive exploration draws on Plasticity; rumination draws on Withdrawal, low Industriousness, and interpersonal deference (Politeness). Behaviourally, this results in Diffusion and Moratorium correlating with procrastination ($r = .22$ and $.30$ respectively), while Achievement correlates negatively ($r = -0.34$) and Foreclosure shows no relationship.^[39]

The DIDS scale demonstrates that conformity is not a unitary construct but can be decomposed into simple behavioural conformity (Carefree Diffusion) or behavioural conformity and psychological identification therewith (Foreclosure). Because in Foreclosure conformity is internalized rather than reflexive, goals may remain stable even if the deontic cues in the environment change. The identification with commitment characteristic of Foreclosure has also been associated with greater well-being^[37], possibly because identity serves as an internal system of measurement that reduces uncertainty, even in the absence of environmental cues. The DIDS is capable of assessing the process of goal selection, but not goal origin. I hypothesize that it will be possible to make a distinction between the striver and Nietzschean types via new scales assessing metacognitive awareness of goal origin, and applying endogenous success criteria. This is a priority for future research, along with a proper unification of identity and its temporal dynamics under active inference.

5.4 Persuadability

One key feature of Michael Levin's work on agents is to assess where they lie on a spectrum of persuadability,^[40] where persuadability is defined based on the types of inputs that are required to change an agent's behaviour through modifying the goals it tries to pursue. A system like a thermostat is persuadable by modifying its temperature setpoint, a dog is persuadable via training with food rewards, and a human is persuadable via emotional or logical arguments. Persuadability is key for understanding agency because it is the mechanism through which one agent can modify the agentic scope of a different agent. A system that is too persuadable, or where the levers required to persuade it are too legible or easily accessed, is at risk of being exploited for the benefit of anything that can manipulate those levers. This is true at the level of the *Cordyceps* fungus modifying insect behaviour, up to the level of emotional or propagandistic manipulation in humans.⁶

⁶The picture is not always this simple. *Toxoplasma gondii* increases risk-taking in both mice and wolves by modulating dopamine and testosterone. In mice this is unambiguously parasitic: bolder mice approach predators and are eaten, completing the parasite's lifecycle. But in wolves, Meyer et al. (2022)^[54] found that infected Yellowstone wolves were roughly 11 times more likely to disperse and 46 times more likely to become pack leaders. These are outcomes that plausibly benefit the wolf as well as the parasite. Wolves are apex predators for whom risk-taking and dominance competition are adaptive, so neurochemical manipulation that increases boldness may be mutualistic rather than parasitic in this species. Whether sub-rational manipulation constitutes a vulnerability thus depends on whether the induced behaviour is maladaptive in the host's environment – for prey species under predation pressure, increased boldness is lethal; for apex predators, it may be net positive, physiological costs of infection aside. A human analogue would be a wife who manipulates her husband into greater ambition through emotional pressure rather than rational argument (indeed men may select for wives who do this). This bypasses his highest level of evaluation, but if the resulting behaviour serves his interests as well as hers, the manipulation is mutualistic. Lady Macbeth is the canonical literary example, though it illustrates the catastrophic failure case. This parallels the role of environmental threat in determining whether agentic phenotypes are adaptive, discussed later.

Agency requires persuadability; unpersuadable systems like mechanical clocks possess no agency at all. As systems ascend the hierarchy of persuadability they gain agency via incorporating subsystems operating at every lower level. A human contains homeostatic processes responsive to chemical signals, conditioning systems responsive to reward and punishment, and emotional systems responsive to social pressure. In a coherent agent, the Self subsumes and coordinates all of these subsystems in service of its goals, and accordingly an agent should only be open to *exogenous* persuasion at the highest level it can attain. For humans, this is rational, evidence-based argument. Persuasion that operates below this level bypasses the Self. When spending is shaped by operant conditioning, or political convictions shifted by emotional appeals, the individual's goals are being redirected without rational evaluation. Complete imperviousness to persuasion at more basal levels is unrealistic, but every lever that can be accessed below the highest level is a point of vulnerability through which an agent's goals can be co-opted. This concern applies strictly to exogenous manipulation; an individual who deliberately conditions his own habits or emotional responses is exercising agency, not compromising it, since the conditioning serves goals set by the Self.

Therefore a maximally agentic individual must be persuadable by rational, evidence-based argument, and resist persuasion through exogenous emotional manipulation or classical/operant conditioning. An individual who cannot be persuaded by reasoned arguments must default to being persuaded either by emotional manipulation, or by normative cues, i.e. appeal to authority or convention. Although there is no data explicitly studying the level of cognitive ability required to understand complex evidence-based arguments, this can be inferred based on literacy and numeracy data collected by the Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC). A level 4 on the PIAAC literacy test corresponds to an ability to comprehend a dense text across multiple pages with distracting information and complete a task with implicit demands.^[41] Compared to a level 3, level 4 must handle longer texts with much more distracting information, and complete tasks with fewer explicit instructions. For instance, evaluating an argument in a blog post (level 3) versus analyzing and synthesizing contradictory sources (level 4). While a level 3 might be able to comprehend a logical argument, a literacy level of 4 would be required to decide *between* logical arguments without resorting to appeals to authority or convention. In the United States, 44

In numeracy, a level 3 corresponds to the ability to read a simple chart and evaluate whether an arithmetic claim (e.g. a percentage discount on a sale) is accurate. Level 4 corresponds to the ability to interpret graphs containing multiple variables, or determine whether a basic statistical claim is supported by data. Level 5 corresponds to

performing basic statistical modeling. In the United States, 38

While increases in information processing ability are useful, they must be actively employed to be of any help. Decreases in agency occur when motivation for action is devolved from higher-order logical egoistic processes to lower processes like emotional salience or base urges like hunger or lust. In fact, research into persuasion has demonstrated that falling for scams is not linked solely to IQ, but to momentarily suspending rational decision making long enough to be victimized. Susceptibility to scams is a valuable measure of persuadability. Persuasion must be accompanied by a change in behaviour, otherwise there is no empirical basis from which to argue that persuasion occurred. With scams, behaviour is changed in a way that is costly to the victim, and thus represents a decrease in agentic capacity.

In one study of 151 seniors, reduced cognitive ability was the most significant predictor of scam victimization ($d = 0.65$ between victims and non-victims on the self-report MASQ scale).^[43] The Susceptibility to Persuasion scale was developed to predict scam compliance, and found that in order of effect size, Social Influence (related to Agreeableness), inverse Self-Control (Conscientiousness), Need for Uniqueness (Openness), Sensation Seeking (Extraversion), and inverse Need for Cognition (Intellect) all predicted finding a fraudulent offer plausible.^[44] The strongest predictor of responding to a scam was finding it plausible in the first place, and the strongest predictor of being scammed was responding.

The full model explains only 5-10

5.5 Risk Preference

All high agency people must take risks. Part of being high agency is the ability to capitalize on opportunities that others miss, either because they are unwilling to accept the risk of doing so, or because they lack the ability to identify that the opportunities exist. Risk preference increases the scope of goals an agent is willing to adopt.

Self-report measures of risk taking across domains like investment, recreation, and socialization all correlate, and a general factor R can be extracted.^[45] Behavioural measures of risk (e.g. laboratory gambling tasks) do not correlate well with each other or with psychometric measures, consistent with the general finding that behavioural tasks have lower reliability than self-report psychometrics.^[46] However, psychometric measures and propensity measures (how often one actually engages in various risky behaviours) are highly correlated.

The general factor R is predicted positively by Openness ($\beta^*=0.20$) and Extraversion ($\beta^*=0.19$) and negatively by Conscientiousness ($\beta^*=-0.25$) and Agreeableness ($\beta^*=-$

0.13). This pattern – positive loadings on the Plasticity traits and negative loadings on the Conscientiousness and Agreeableness subset of Stability – recapitulates Agency and Communion. High risk tolerance is associated with exploratory, reward-seeking behaviour and is inhibited by traits that prioritize social harmony and impulse suppression.

Impulsivity is related to but distinct from risk preference. Impulsivity as a trait breaks down psychometrically into lack of Premeditation and Perseverance (facets of Conscientiousness, representing planning and following through), and presence of Urgency (threat salience, related to Neuroticism) and Sensation Seeking (reward salience, related to Extraversion).^[55] Self-report impulsivity scales correlate with each other, and a general impulsivity factor *I* can be extracted which predicts behaviours like compulsive buying, compulsive eating, and excessive social media use.^[47] The distinction between adaptive risk-taking and maladaptive impulsivity may lie in the involvement of Conscientiousness: risk-taking that is premeditated and in service of long-term goals differs from impulsive risk-taking driven by urgency or sensation seeking without regard for consequences.

6 Agentic Environment and Evolutionary Pressures

Regardless of the ambitions and capabilities of an agent, the environment in which he acts determines the ultimate extent of the goals he is able to achieve. An ambitious and highly capable individual who is marooned on a desert island or locked in prison will not be able to demonstrate a high level of achievement due to his impoverished and constrained conditions. To go one step further, there are even some environments where the exercise of a high degree of agency is actively harmful.

While agency may seem like an untrammelled good in the current social atmosphere, like all traits it is subject to evolutionary selection pressures. While one's environment may be more or less conducive to the successful achievement of one's goals, it can also punish the attempt. Agency is risky, in both personal and evolutionary terms. Thus, different populations which evolved in different environments were selected to display different degrees of agency. The Inuit are a quintessential example, with an essentially anti-agentic phenotype:

Inuit personality is generally described as emotionally controlled/repressed, calm, deferential, harmony seeking, pragmatic, reserved, introverted, stoic, unassertive, nonconfrontational, and self-sufficient^[48]

This is the result of extreme selection for communion at the expense of agency. In the arctic, conditions are extreme and risk is omnipresent. Small missteps can lead

to death, like getting caught out in inclement weather or pursuing game onto an ice floe that breaks off and floats away. It also requires cohabitating in close quarters with your band for days or weeks at a time while waiting out a blizzard. Under such conditions agentic risk taking is harshly punished and competition leads to social friction. This leads to the agentic phenotype being strongly selected against. This is not to say that the Inuit are maladapted to their environment or incompetent, but that, as noted earlier, agentic scope is orthogonal to competence.

The harshness of the environment is also reflected in the Inuit worldview:

Inuit scholars generalize the Inuit worldview as dangerously uncertain, impermanent, and constantly changing and the resulting epistemology as theoretically unknowable, with the degree of knowability of an observation characterized by its immediate practicality and usability. (Briggs, 1991 as cited in Sun^[48])

This epistemic posture, while adaptive in context, strongly curtails the temporal domain of agentic scope. Long term plans are infeasible when the environment in which those plans unfold is so variable.

The Inuit case illustrates a general principle: agency is fundamentally about bearing costs. An agentic individual takes risks, pursues goals with uncertain outcomes, and absorbs the consequences of failure. This is only a viable strategy when the environment permits it. Where errors are routinely lethal and conditions unpredictable, the price of agentic risk-taking exceeds what any individual can bear, and selection favours communal, risk-averse phenotypes instead. Environments that select for high agency must be harsh enough to demand the intelligence and conscientiousness required for long-term planning, but open enough to reward those who plan well and act decisively. The distribution of agency in a population is therefore a product of the selection pressures that shaped it, and in turn constrains the population-level phenotype, like social organization and institution design.

7 Big Five and Career Success

Is there broad empirical support for the relationship between the psychometric parameters discussed here and life outcomes? In one Dutch study of 1,940 people,^[49] OLS regression found that Openness and Extraversion positively predicted income, while Agreeableness and Neuroticism predicted it negatively. Once education and profession were included in the model, Openness was no longer predictive, which suggests that the benefit of Openness is that it increases the complexity scope of goals that one can achieve, which is usually associated with higher remuneration. Once you control

for the complexity scale that you are operating at, Openness is no longer predictive.

A different data set of over 40,000 UK households^[50] found that IQ was by far the strongest predictor of three measures: income, occupational prestige, and occupational status. Conscientiousness was predictive even after residualizing for intelligence. Agreeableness was negatively predictive of income but slightly positive for occupational status and prestige. Extraversion was actually negatively predictive even when residualized for IQ in this data set, though other studies have found positive relationships. Neuroticism was negatively predictive as expected. Willingness to take risks (measured with a single question) was positively predictive of income. After residualizing for IQ, Openness had very little effect.

These findings are broadly consistent with the theory outlined here: IQ is central to agency through its effects on perception, world-modeling, and persuadability; Conscientiousness contributes through prioritization of long-term goals; Neuroticism detracts through withdrawal from goal-directed behaviour; and the picture for Extraversion and Agreeableness is more complex, potentially depending on the specific aspect (Assertiveness vs Enthusiasm, Compassion vs Politeness) and the specific outcome measure.

8 Conclusion

Given this theoretical framing and review of the literature, we would expect maximally agentic individuals to be high in Assertiveness, Industriousness, and Intellect, moderate to high in Openness to Experience, moderate in Enthusiasm and Orderliness, moderate to low in Compassion, and low in Politeness and both aspects of Neuroticism. They would be highly intelligent, developing and pursuing their own goals unconstrained by social expectations or norms. They would strive for power, achievement, and superiority in whatever domain they chose, while retaining enough affiliative capacity to build sustainable coalitions in pursuit of their objectives. They would be ready and willing to take risks in furtherance of their goals, and if they did not find themselves in an environment that rewarded risk-taking they would migrate to or niche construct an environment that did.

The profile above is described in terms of the Big Five and other psychometrics, but these do not exhaust the parameters relevant to agency. The cognitive phenotypes identified by computational psychiatry – like those underlying autism or schizotypy, discussed earlier – are another class of variables which we are now beginning to be able to measure. Future research will need to enumerate and categorize the relevant parameters, and empirically investigate their relationship to agency. We know from

ancient DNA analyses that these traits have been under directional selection over the past 12,000 years as the human informational environment has changed, with autism becoming more common and schizophrenia less common.^{[51],[52]} Different cognitive phenotypes may have distinct impacts agentic expression, especially as human social and informatic environments have changed dramatically over this time period.

Psychometrically, the priority is to develop purpose-built scales to assess agentic scope in its spatial, temporal, and complexity dimensions. This would enable direct testing of the hypotheses that Conscientiousness predicts long temporal scope, Extraversion predicts expansive spatial scope, and IQ predicts goal complexity. Additional scales should also be developed to assess the empirical tenability of the striver-Nietzschean distinction, under the hypothesis that it is a product of metacognitive awareness of goal origin and endogenous success criteria. The measurement of persuadability also needs to be improved, although this may not be possible using exclusively psychometric methods. Finally, the dynamics of agentic scope across the lifespan should be studied, including its relationship to personal identity, and how it expands or contracts in response to life events.

This paper has focused on providing a theoretical framework for the quantitative measurement of human agency, and on thoroughly exploring the psychometric basis of agentic scope. Future work will investigate agentic capacity, integrating such research areas like leadership, learned helplessness, and motor learning into the cybernetic idiom. The goal of this paper is to lay the groundwork for a fruitful theoretical paradigm to investigate these questions, incorporating research directions at the frontier of adjacent fields. This helps to ensure the paradigm will be commensurable with the next few decades of research into neuroscience and systems biology. The next steps are to begin collecting empirical data to validate hypotheses, and continue synthesizing relevant past research under this framework.

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